

TOURISM AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN RUSSIA: CURRENT CHALLENGES AND CONSTRAINTS

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Abstract

The sustainable tourism development has become a prerequisite for the industry functioning. Sustainable tourism is now seen as a logical response to a growing tourist flow, and as a result, to an excessive burden on the natural and historical and cultural environment of destinations. In Russia, sustainable development is a complex and painful issue. Ambiguity of responsibility areas and the lack of thoughtful and well-established regulatory mechanisms make the interaction between business and government in sustainable territory development a particularly difficult issue in Russia. That is why the purpose of this study is to reveal how the representatives of the tourism business understand the need for sustainable tourism development in Russia. The survey of business representatives conducted in the article made it possible to identify problems in understanding the essence of sustainable tourism development, and to identify the sustainable tourism trends, which in many ways demonstrate the growing need for the transition of the tourism industry in Russia to the principles of sustainable development. One of the important problems of sustainable tourism development in Russia is the professional personnel training. For this purpose, the authors have developed a combined model of educational activities in the "challenges-needs" system for the sustainable development of hospitality industry. It is intended for stakeholders of the tourism market and is aimed at raising awareness and building sustainable interaction.

Keywords: Sustainable tourism development; Development; Sustainability; Tourism; Management System; Russia.

TURISMO E DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENTÁVEL NA RÚSSIA: DESAFIOS E CONSTRANGIMENTOS ATUAIS**Resumo**

O desenvolvimento do turismo sustentável tornou-se um pré-requisito para o funcionamento da indústria. O turismo sustentável é agora visto como uma resposta lógica a um fluxo turístico crescente e, como resultado, a uma carga excessiva sobre o ambiente natural, histórico e cultural dos destinos. Na Rússia, o desenvolvimento sustentável é uma questão complexa e dolorosa. A ambigüidade das áreas de responsabilidade e a falta de mecanismos reguladores ponderados e bem estabelecidos tornam a interação entre empresas e governo no desenvolvimento sustentável do território uma questão particularmente difícil na Rússia. É por isso que o objetivo deste estudo é revelar como os representantes das empresas de turismo entendem a necessidade de desenvolvimento turístico sustentável na Rússia. O inquérito aos representantes das empresas realizado no artigo permitiu identificar problemas na compreensão da essência do desenvolvimento do turismo sustentável, e identificar as tendências do turismo sustentável, o que demonstra de muitas formas a necessidade crescente da transição da indústria do turismo na Rússia para os princípios do desenvolvimento sustentável. Um dos problemas importantes do desenvolvimento do turismo sustentável na Rússia é a formação de pessoal profissional. Para este fim, o autor desenvolveu um modelo combinado de atividades educacionais no sistema "desafios- necessidades" para o desenvolvimento sustentável da indústria hoteleira. Destina-se aos intervenientes do mercado do turismo e tem como objetivo sensibilizar e construir uma interação sustentável.

Palavras-chave: Desenvolvimento do turismo sustentável; Desenvolvimento; Sustentabilidade; Turismo; Sistema de gestão; Rússia.

TURISMO Y DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE EN RUSIA: RETOS Y LIMITACIONES ACTUALES**Resumen**

El desarrollo del turismo sostenible se ha convertido en un requisito previo para el funcionamiento de la industria. El turismo sostenible se ve ahora como una respuesta lógica a un flujo turístico creciente y, en consecuencia, a una carga excesiva sobre el entorno natural e histórico y cultural de los destinos. En Rusia, el desarrollo sostenible es una cuestión compleja y dolorosa. La ambigüedad de las áreas de responsabilidad y la falta de mecanismos reguladores bien establecidos hacen que la interacción entre las empresas y el gobierno en el desarrollo sostenible del territorio sea una cuestión especialmente difícil en Rusia. Por ello, el objetivo de este estudio es revelar cómo entienden los representantes del negocio turístico la necesidad de un desarrollo turístico sostenible en Rusia. La encuesta realizada a los representantes de las empresas en el artículo permitió identificar los problemas de comprensión de la esencia del desarrollo del turismo sostenible, e identificar las tendencias del turismo sostenible, que en muchos aspectos demuestran la creciente necesidad de la transición de la industria del turismo en Rusia a los principios del desarrollo sostenible. Uno de los problemas importantes del desarrollo del turismo sostenible en Rusia es la formación del personal profesional. Para ello, el autor ha desarrollado un modelo combinado de actividades educativas en el sistema "retos-necesidades" para el desarrollo sostenible de la industria de la hostelería. Está destinado a las partes interesadas del mercado turístico y tiene como objetivo la sensibilización y la creación de una interacción sostenible.

Palabras clave: Desarrollo turístico sostenible; Desarrollo; Sostenibilidad; Turismo; Sistema de gestión; Rusia.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The global challenges posed to humanity, among which the COVID-19 pandemic, diplomatic crises and armed conflicts have the greatest impact on the development of the tourism industry and put sustainable development issues on the top. The traditional and latest sustainable development mechanisms are of importance today. They on the one hand, act as drivers of innovative development of both economies and destinations, and on the other hand, due to the social component, humanize tourism and reduce its negative impact on the socio-cultural environment.

Sustainable tourism is now seen as a logical response to the growing tourist flow, and as a result, to the excessive pressure on the natural and historical-cultural environment of destinations. An example is Machu Picchu, one of the world popular tourist destinations, which is visited by thousands of tourists every day.

Growing demand from tourists a led to the extensive use of this treasures of the world for tourism purposes, which, together with unregulated use, inadequate planning, deficient monitoring mechanisms and weak policy enforcement endangered its existence. As a result, UNESCO has urged the government of Peru to revise its Master Plan for managing the Historic Sanctuary to emphasize sustainable development and prevent Machu Picchu's possible inscription on the list of World Heritage Sites in danger (Regalado-Pezua & Arias-Valencia, 2006). The state is currently working with UNESCO to construct a new Master Plan, but – with many diverse stakeholders and interests to balance – reaching consensus regarding Machu Picchu's future has proven to be extremely difficult (Larson & Poudyal, 2012).

However, despite the apparent evidence of a positive result, sustainable development is a complicated topic. In many ways, it is declarative, utopian in nature. Until now, the mechanisms and possible tools for measuring the sustainability of the industry have not been fully thought out and developed. Many statements and basic principles of sustainability of the tourism industry remain only on paper, not being implemented in practice. Especially there is no correct understanding of sustainable tourism in business, many managers see sustainability only in greening, which today is more of a marketing technique that can increase the value of a product without investing in its quality (Afanasiev et al., 2018).

The tourism transition to the principles of sustainable development in Russia is complicated by the lack of a single state body responsible for the

economy sustainable development, as well as an unclear management system for the sustainable tourism development.

But at the same time, the principles of sustainable development implemented at different levels can harmonize the economy and society, optimize the operation of enterprises and reduce the anthropogenic impact on the environment. Understanding the importance and specifics of the sustainable development of the tourism industry at all levels – from local communities to business and government representatives - is the key to a successful transition to the basic principles of sustainable development. That is why the purpose of this study is to reveal how the representatives of the tourism business understand the need for sustainable tourism development in Russia.

The objectives of the study include the study of existing views and gaps in the scientific literature regarding the mechanisms of sustainable development, the formulation of a model for sustainable interaction among stakeholders in the tourism market, a description of the features of the sustainable development of the tourism industry in Russia, an analysis of the understanding by representatives of the tourism business sustainable development issues and development the proposals to improve the identified shortcomings.

2 REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC SOURCES

According to World Federation of Natural and National Parks sustainable tourism development is all forms of tourism development and management that do not contradict the natural, social, economic unity and well-being of established societies in an indefinite period.

Tourist Concern and Wild World Fund state that the sustainable tourism development is ensured within the limits of environmental sustainability, allows to effectively restoring the productivity of natural resources, considering the contribution of local communities to tourists' recreation; provides for the local population rights equality to the economic benefits from tourism; puts the wishes and needs of the host destination first.

The sustainable tourism development allows the modern inhabitants of the planet to satisfy their own needs for recreation and recreation without the threat of loss of this opportunity by future generations (according to UNDP, Production and consumption branch).

According to the World Tourism Organization, sustainable tourism is "tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of

visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities” (DESA UN, 2022).

The issues of sustainable tourism are especially popular in the scientific community. They receive the most attention from both scientists and government officials. At the same time, without a scientific approach it is impossible to develop and measure the effectiveness of implementation of the sustainable development principles.

To date, thousands of articles and monographs have been written on the sustainable tourism industry. The issues of sustainable development received special attention regarding the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent rapid changes in the tourism business around the world.

Many destinations that depend on tourism, including ecotourism, have suffered catastrophic effects on their economies, calling into question the sustainability of ecotourism as a whole. However, even in the pre-pandemic period, a skeptical attitude was formed in the scientific community towards understanding sustainable tourism as equal to ecological tourism.

Ecotourism, alternative tourism, responsible tourism, soft tourism, low-impact tourism, community tourism, and so on are considered in an optimistic way, as the path to sustainable tourism development. But experiences show that none of these forms can be relied on as the way forward for a sustainable and growing tourism industry worldwide (Liu, 2003).

In general, scientific publications on sustainable tourism development can be grouped into the following areas:

- review articles devoted to the analysis of existing publications on the topic of sustainable development and tourism (Bac, 2014; Butler, 1999; Lu & Nepal, 2009; Streimikiene et al., 2021);
- critical articles on the essence of sustainable development (Toman, 1992; Hunter, 1995; Liu, 2003; Burrai, Buda & Stanford, 2019);
- theoretical works on terminology, mechanisms and definitions of sustainable tourism (Clarke, 1997; Hardy et al., 2002; Harris et al., 2012; Angelevska-Najdeska & Rakicevik, 2012; Hall, 2019);
- research articles that study the mechanisms of sustainable development, successful practices and ways to transform the industry in the key to sustainable development (Bramwell, 1998; Miller, 2001; Schianetz & Kavanagh, 2008; Sutawa, 2012);
 - regional articles that are dedicated to sustainable tourism in the world's tourist destinations, regions or individual areas

(Barke & Newton, 1995; Larson & Poudyal, 2012; Wang et al., 2016; Ramyasri, 2021; Bakas & Duxbury, 2019; McNicol, 2016).

In view of the research objective, we studied scientific publications dedicated to issues of human resources as a key factor in the industry sustainability. There are few such works, and it demonstrates a misunderstanding of the personnel importance in ensuring sustainable development (for example, Tohid Ardahaey & Nabiloo, 2012; Sandaruwani & Gnanapala, 2016).

However, existing works emphasize the importance of the human factor in the industry sustainability, including line workers. Thus, Sandaruwani and Gnanapala (2016) have studied the role of guides in creation of a sustainable tourism product in Sri Lanka.

After all, it is the guides who become «unofficial ambassadors of the host country» (Sandaruwani and Gnanapala, 2016), capable of both giving an unforgettable tourist experience to visitors, and creating a need for the consumption of a sustainable territorial product in their own country and on further travels. At the same time, guides are often representatives of local communities, so their model of sustainable consumption can be an example for both countrymen and tourists.

Thus, we can summarize the review of scientific literature. In scientific publications on sustainable development, the issues of overtourism and the irrational use of tourist resources are today largely put at the forefront.

To a lesser extent, sustainable tourism is seen as a way to improve the efficiency of the industry. But despite the seeming declarative basis of sustainable development, several authors say that sustainable development mechanisms can be adopted by both individual enterprises and regional authorities. Sustainable development today is the key to building competitive advantages. Sustainable tourism development is closely linked to payment attention to a consumer as this allows to attract more consumers, expand business and increase competitiveness (Luekveerawattana, 2018).

Streimikiene et al. (2021) tried to understand what are the current prospects of sustainable tourism in consolidation with the competitiveness of a tourism sector.

An alarming moment is the fact that many researchers consider sustainable tourism as a form of ecological tourism and see its development through the mechanisms for introducing green and resource-saving technologies.

The issues of involving personnel of different levels in ensuring the sustainable development of destinations occupy a modest place in the scientific literature. Considerable attention is paid to line personnel working directly with tourists and employees in the government. That is why it is important to study how business representatives at the level of middle and top management are involved in the sustainable tourism development.

3 METHODOLOGY

Tourism development is both supply-led and demand-driven (Liu, 2003). That is why the sustainable tourism development is impossible without balanced and coordinated actions of all the stakeholders of the process. A review of scientific publications makes it possible to form the stakeholder sustainable interaction model for tourist destination (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The stakeholder sustainable interaction model for tourist destination

Source: own elaboration, 2022.

Thus, the authorities have the task of sustainable management and monitoring of the environment and the market, the business – careful, rational production, the locals and tourists – rational consumption and use of resources. At the same time, along with creating a “sustainable” tourist offer, it is important to manage the demand for sustainable tourist products, promote careful consumption and awareness, including during tourist trips. can be solved by the joint efforts of the authorities and business.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The sustainable Tourism Management System in Russian Federation

The Concept of the Russian economy transition to sustainable development was approved in 1996 (Decree, 1996), and it was the starting point for implementing the basic principles of sustainable development in the country (Yakimchuk et al., 2021). The Concept is aimed at balanced solving socio-economic problems and the preservation of a favorable environment and natural resource potential as the condition for transition to sustainable development.

The sustainable development goals adopted in the UN Agenda 2030 (GDGs) are integrated into

national projects, as well as strategic and policy documents. The national projects are adjusted considering the national development goals until 2030, which directly echo the SDGs (Yakimchuk et al., 2021).

The lack of a single authority responsible for achieving the SDGs is one of the problems in achieving the SDGs in Russia. De facto, individual public authorities are responsible for SDGs attainment related to the direction of their activities, so they implement the measures in accordance with the available powers.

The Federal Agency for Tourism (Rosturizm) plays key role in the management of the tourism industry in Russia, and today it is directly subordinate to the Government of the Russian Federation. This is a federal executive body that implements the state tourism policy, supervises tourism activities, and coordinates tourism market entities. The activities of the Federal Agency for Tourism, as well as all statutory, regulatory and strategic documents, are built on the basic principles of sustainable development.

However, today there are no tools for stimulating and monitoring the enterprises in matters of sustainable and responsible operations. In Russia there is no single program for the transition to sustainable development, as well as a separate roadmap for the implementation of the SDGs, most of the sustainable development tasks at the national level are implemented through

state socio-economic development programs, including subprograms and departmental targeted programs.

Today in Russia there are no state standards and requirements for the organization of the tourism and hotel business that meets the principles of sustainable development. The Green Standard developed in 2022 became practically an innovation for tourism infrastructure.

The standard was developed by the Research Institute for Sustainable Development in Construction. It can be the basis for the building hotels, recreation centers, campsites, glampings that meet the principles of sustainable development. The standard does not contradict Russian building codes, but contains broader and deeper requirements for structures, engineering systems, materials and landscaping. Objects that meet the Green Standard will have higher environmental and consumer qualities.

However, this example rather demonstrates the lack of a unified approach to managing the sustainable development of tourism. In addition, there are no mechanisms for implementing this standard and monitoring its compliance.

A pool of public organizations is engaged in the sphere of tourism industry sustainable development. The Country Sustainable Development Coalition (CSDC) studies efficiency and implementation problems of SDGs in Russia.

CSDC prepared the Citizens Review on the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals, which analyzes the current situation in the field of each of the 17 SDGs and presents the recommendations for the state and civil society on their achievement, as well as on the ways for cooperation between the state and civil society (Decade, 2020).

The review was prepared before the worldwide COVID-19 crisis, so the materials and recommendations are provided without considering the socio-economic changes occurred in Russia in the spring of 2020.

The Committee for the Sustainable Tourism Development under the Russian Union of Tourism Industry is an important public organization that deals with issues of sustainable tourism in the country. The Committee has been studying advanced sustainable development technologies for a long time. However, this is a public organization that does not have effective mechanisms for influencing business.

Today in Russia, due to the growing domestic tourism market, an increasing number of participants, both public organizations and authorities, are involved in addressing sustainable development issues, but the mechanisms of their interaction are not fully developed.

4.2 The Place of Business in the Sustainable Tourism Development in Russia

The positive practices of sustainable tourism already exist in Russia. Basically, these are small and less often medium-sized businesses that operate in the field of rural and out-of-town tourism. In big business, entire councils and committees for sustainable development have been created, but in practice, very little is being done to achieve the SDGs.

Golubino Forest Hotel is an example of successful tourism enterprise that operates on the principles of sustainable development. Its mission of the is not only to develop tourist business in a single place, but also to promote the sustainable development of the entire Arkhangelsk region, through creating new jobs and promoting care for nature of the region.

Many young people leave Russia's small town, and this a negative trend leads to the dying of the Russian hinterland. Golubino Forest Hotel (2022) not only provides jobs, but also makes the Russian northern village attractive for tourists and workers. The park implements social projects and supports locals.

From a small business, this enterprise has turned into an important tourist and social center of the whole region. However, there are very few such enterprises in Russia, and they don't illustrate the entire tourism industry. Today, the tourist market in Russia is represented by thousands of travel agencies, tour operators of various sizes, cruise companies, tour agencies, etc.

An important trend is the emergence of organizers of so-called "authorial" (experiential) tours, which, it would seem, whose business is based precisely on the tourism sustainability and awareness. However, is it really the case, or sustainability is nothing more than a marketing technique, is not clear (Afanasieva & Afanasiev, 2021).

That is why we conducted a survey among representatives of the tourism business to identify their understanding of the sustainable development principles and the level of readiness for the transition to them, as well as civic responsibility and awareness in this matter. We studied the opinions of employees of travel agencies, tour operators, sightseeing and excursions agencies, authors of experiential tourism products and other enterprises that are involved in the provision of tourism services.

We developed a questionnaire and sent it to members of professional communities, unions, groups in social networks. A total of 680 employees from all regions of Russia participated in the survey. The questions of the questionnaire and the results of the survey are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Survey of employees of tourism enterprises: the questions and generalized answers

Questions	Generalized answers and their ratio			
Type of enterprise (total number by the groups)	Travel agency - 344	Sightseeing and excursion agency - 26	Organizer of experiential tours - 223	Tour operator - 15
	Accommodation facilities - 35	Tourist attractions - 15	Tourist information center - 20	Travel Literature Publisher - 2
Respondent's position	Head of the enterprise - 220	Department head - 287	Manager - 163	Other - 10
Choose words analogous to the term "sustainable tourism" (multiple choice)	Eco friendly - 91%	Green - 56%	Effective - 24%	Safe - 46%
	Alternative - 26%	Not massive - 32%	Innovative - 35%	Balanced - 15%
Do you apply the principles of sustainable tourism in your work?	Yes - 15%	No, but I would like to use it - 38%	I don't use, and I don't think it's possible - 46%	Find it difficult to answer - 1%
How many sustainable development goals can you list?	Over 10 goals - 0,5%	From 5 to 10 goals - 2%	A few - 41%	Find it difficult to answer - 56,5%
Do you agree that sustainable development is a technology that can increase the efficiency of an enterprise?	I agree - 38%	I rather agree - 22%	I rather disagree - 25%	I disagree - 15%
How much are you willing to pay for training your employees in sustainable development?	More than 1000 USD - 2%	From 250 to 1000 USD - 8%	Not more than 250 USD - 35%	Not ready to pay - 55%
How much are you willing to pay for self-education in sustainable development	More than 1000 USD - 10%	From 250 to 1000 USD - 15 %	Not more than 250 USD - 45%	Not ready to pay - 30%
Have you been trained in sustainability programs?	No - 55%	Yes, in courses of basic education - 35%	Yes, in courses of additional education - 1,5%	Yes, within the programs of public organizations and international funds - 8,5%
Are you satisfied with the overall results of the training?	I satisfied - 28%	I rather satisfied - 32%	I'm rather dissatisfied - 25%	I am not satisfied - 15%
Mark the most important results that you received in the learning process (multiple choice)	I learned about the sustainable development principles, SDGs -98%	I learned about lean manufacturing - 12%	I raised my awareness -45%	SDG Documentation Skills - 20%
	I studied the mechanisms of sustainable development - 25%	I studied international documents and standards on sustainable development - 18%	I learned about successful cases and benefits for market participants - 65%	I learned how to apply the principles and SDGs to optimize the enterprise operation - 4%
Indicate what you specifically did not like about training (multiple choice)	Declarative and excessive theorization of the material - 80%	It is not clear how to apply all this in work - 60%	Lack of detailed analysis of practical cases - 35%	Lack of related internships - 28%
Can you give examples of sustainable tourism businesses or destinations around the world? (multiple choice)	Northern European countries - 62%	Australia - 15%	Southeast Asia - 28%	Find it difficult to answer - 28%
	Caribbean countries - 45%	Southern European countries - 18 %	North American countries - 8%	Other destinations (one answer per country) - 10%
Do you agree that there are many examples of sustainable tourism enterprises in Russia?	I agree - 22%	I rather agree - 28%	I rather disagree - 37%	I disagree - 13%
Who should be responsible for the sustainable development of destinations?	Authorities - 77%	Business with the support of the authorities - 13%	Local communities and tourists - 8 %	Find it difficult to answer - 2%
What are the important, in your opinion, mechanisms for the sustainable development of tourism? (multiple choice)	Public policy - 89%	Certification and standardization - 56%	Implementation of energy and resource saving technologies - 48%	Fair competition - 25%
	lean consumption - 32%	Waste sorting - 32%	Education - 31%	Find it difficult to answer - 2%
Do you agree that your business contributes to SDG 8 *?	I agree - 18%	I rather agree - 35%	I rather disagree - 37%	I disagree - 10%

* Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
Source: own elaboration.

4.3 Results and Discussions

Thus, it is obvious that representatives of the tourism business in Russia do not fully understand the essence of sustainable tourism and do not see its application in their activities. Most often, employees of tourism enterprises associate the concept of sustainable tourism with environmental friendliness and frugality of resources.

In the total amount of responses, less than half of all employees use or are ready to apply the mechanisms and principles of sustainable development in their activities. A significant part of the respondents noted that public authorities should be responsible for the sustainable development of destinations. About 100 respondents agreed to give more detailed answers, and the-depth interview revealed that employees consider the transition to sustainable development to be costly and not justified. Many note that sustainability in general is a good trend, but in Russia there is no way to develop it.

It must be said that travel and excursion agencies in Russia are represented by small and medium-sized businesses, as well as significant part of the accommodation facilities. This is a low-margin business, in which there are no free funds for expanding activities and educating employees. Many travel agencies have a cost-cutting strategy, which is why they do not consider other ways to build competitive advantage.

Tourist information centers in Russia are mostly state-owned. Only one private tourist information center is represented in our selection, however, and in the total amount of such enterprises in the country, private tourist information centers occupy a very modest place. State tourist information centers can count on funding and subsidies from the state budget, so their employees have more opportunities to be trained in sustainable development programs. In addition, employees of tourist information centers show higher creativity in their responses, they are more aware of the sustainable development goals, mechanisms and practices of sustainable tourism.

Representatives of accommodation facilities unanimously equate sustainable tourism and green technologies. In this regard, representatives of small hotels would like to introduce green technologies in their enterprises or are already implementing them.

Tourism literature publishing houses are represented in the survey by the head of the department and the editor-in-chief of a large enterprise. These are people with a high level of education who not only understand the essence of sustainable tourism, but also apply the principles of sustainable development in their activities.

Thus, as measures to promote the SDGs, they noted creating tourists' awareness through the content of publications, the stimulating the demand for careful consumption of tourism services and sustainable destinations, the promotion of places for travelling that meet the requirements of sustainability.

In general, the analysis of the answers makes it possible to identify such problematic points in the understanding of the principles of sustainable territory development by business:

- business representatives don't clearly understand the features of the sustainable development of the tourism industry, areas of responsibility, mechanisms and management tools, as well as they don't know enough about successful practices in Russia and abroad;

- sustainable tourism development is seen as a theory that is difficult to put into practice, or as a costly and inefficient measure;

- business representatives have no idea how it is possible to use the sustainable development principles in their enterprise; they don't see their role in solving global problems on the way to sustainable development;

- many employees are not ready to spend money on self-development and self-education in sustainable development issues.

In addition, based on the study of best practices, expert opinions and general tendencies in the tourism industry, it is possible to characterize the sustainable development trends in the tourism industry.

1. *The rapid development of sustainable tourism and the growing demand for sustainable destinations.* According to expert, the number of people concerned about the state of the planet is growing. Ecological, social and psychological trouble develops in some people the need to change their own attitude towards nature and society, in others – to actively participate in the protection and preservation of the environment, in the third – the most conscious – in restoration. Some part of the people, not limited by their own efforts, seeks to attract supporters to their active work. All this leads to the demand for recreation in sustainable areas, and consequently, to an increase in the tourist flow to such destinations.

2. *Expansion of the geography and types of sustainable tourism, along with the continuing industry's negative impact on society and the nature of individual destinations.* On the one hand, there are new solutions in lean production, on the other hand, in developing countries, tourism is still accompanied by irrational wages for the poor, prostitution, child labor, the leveling of local traditions and excessive pressure on natural areas.

3. *Active development of supranational structures and mechanisms for managing ecological tourism at the international level.* The number of programs and initiatives at the international and regional levels is growing, on the UNWTO initiative, institutions are being formed to monitor sustainability in tourism, and the zones of influence of already existing international organizations are expanding.

4. *Diversification of offer and demand.* The demand for sustainable and eco-friendly activities is growing, but at the same time, the specifics of demand are becoming more complicated.

There are requests for a combination of different forms of tourism, for example, eco-tourism and adventure activities, or ecotourism and cognitive activities, which leads to equipping specially protected areas with sky parks, panda parks, ziplines, etc., increasing popularity of excursion in the natural environment, the growth in number of yoga tours in natural areas, emergence of elements of gastronomic and agricultural forms of tourism in ecotourism programs, etc.

5. *The growing popularity of a healthy lifestyle and the impact on the demand for recreation in the natural environment.* Active promotion of healthy lifestyles is reflected in the growth of both sustainable destinations and natural areas offering a range of physical activities combined with scenic landscapes.

6. *Changing the structure of the tourist flow.* The modern tourist flow is characterized by a wide range of participants' ages – from small and even infants with parents to older tourists. This indicates the growth of the segment of tourists with limited mobility. All this requires an accessible environment for tourists with limited mobility, infrastructure for families with children, the expansion of socio-cultural programs and the introduction of additional activity into tourist destinations (for example, the arrangement of children's play areas, additional places of rest on the route for the elderly, improvement of medical facilities, etc.).

7. *Individualization of travel* – an increasing number of travelers organize their holidays on their own, they also prefer individual trips.

8. *Smartphoneization, digitalization and the impact of social networks on the choice of destinations.* The picturesque nature of natural areas and the influence of social networks on the modern way of life leads to the need for visiting natural areas, including for hedonistic and narcissistic reasons, in order to subsequently post photos on the network and get the approval of society. This, in turn, affects the choice of destinations and places for recreation.

9. *Transition of the tourism industry to the experience economy principles.* Many successful

destinations use immersive technologies in various activities, for example, augmented reality, quest technologies, motivational inscriptions, entertainment and animation activity in natural areas, etc.

10. *Increased security requirements,* which in the context of the pandemic and after it will lead to an increase in attention to sustainable destinations.

11. *A clear course towards sustainable development has been formed in Russia,* that makes obvious the need to optimize tourism industry facilities in accordance with the request of society and the environment.

As a result, we have developed an educational model for stakeholders in the tourism market, aimed at increasing awareness and building sustainable interaction. It is based on understanding of sustainable tourism by business and government representatives, as well as considering current development trends of the tourism industry in Russia.

The developed educational model can be implemented by combining different educational activities within each discipline.

The model can be implemented within the cooperation between educational and research organizations, authorities and enterprises of the tourism industry, as well as with the involvement of public and international organizations. Each discipline can be implemented on its own, or in conjunction with other disciplines of model.

The mosaic nature of the model allows constructing an understanding of the essence and mechanisms of sustainable development based on the existing experience of specific employees. Monitoring and planning of educational activities in this model is based on the challenges and needs of the industry in terms of sustainable development.

The model is aimed at business representatives - both top management and ordinary personnel, government employees, who involved in planning the tourist destination development, teachers, as well as future specialists mastering the basics of hospitality at the level of secondary vocational education, bachelor's and master's degrees. Mosaic nature of the model and the ability to combine its components according to the Lego principle, makes it possible to consider the level of training, and also link the goals and learning outcomes at different stages of educational processes.

As we found out above, modern training programs in Russia, dedicated sustainable development, have excessive theorizing of the material and, as a result, students' lack of understanding of the practical significance of the principles of sustainable development in the tourism and hospitality industry. The substantive part of the model is aimed at solving this problem.

Figure 2 – Combined model of educational activity in the "challenges-needs" system for hospitality industry sustainable development.

The sustainable development in tourism: the basic concepts and main trends *	Name of educational disciplines
<i>For business representatives. How to make the business sustainable</i>	Learning goals
Models and mechanisms of sustainable development of enterprises. Standards and mechanisms for assessing the sustainability of enterprises in relation to organizations in tourism	Questions revealing the content of disciplines
A	Level of training B - Basic, M - intermediate, A - advanced
Project accelerators	Educational activities, the combination of which allows studying disciplines

Legend: Explanations for the figure 2.

Source: Self elaboration, 2022.

The introduction of corporate social responsibility practices, which mainly affect the issues of sustainable development, remains an important issue for Russian tourism business. Unfortunately, today in Russia this concept is inherent in large corporations, and only a very small part of them is associated with tourism. This model is designed to show successful practices of corporate social responsibility and dispel the myth that only large business needs and has enough resource to maintain it.

This model is currently being tested at the Russian State University of Tourism and Service, as well as in a number of other higher educational institutions in Moscow. Its elements have been introduced into training courses at the undergraduate and graduate levels, and into programs of additional professional education. In the future, based on the educational results, this model can be adjusted and improved.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The modern development of the tourism industry actualizes the issues of its transition to sustainable development. It is sustainable tourism that is now seen as a response to the growing tourist flow, its uneven distribution in tourist destinations, the growing negative impact of tourism on local communities and the economies of countries in the face of military operations and diplomatic conflicts, natural disasters and other threats.

The issues of sustainable development are especially popular in the scientific community. However, at the same time, there is a certain bias towards environmental safety and anthropogenic pressure on destinations. To a lesser extent, sustainable tourism is seen to improve the efficiency of the industry.

In the scientific literature, the issues of involving personnel of different levels in ensuring the sustainable development of destinations get a little attention. The model of sustainable interaction among stakeholders of the destination, formed in the article, shows the need for rational and balanced integration and cooperation in the sustainable tourism development of the territory.

In the sustainable tourism management system in Russia, the following problems can be noted: the lack of a single authority responsible for achieving the SDGs, the shortage of state standards and requirements for the tourism and hotel business that meets the sustainable development principles, the ill-conceived mechanisms for achieving the SDGs, the low interest of big business in the sustainable development of territories, etc.

A survey of representatives of the tourism business revealed problems in understanding the essence of sustainable tourism development, their place in this issue, as well as how the basic principles of sustainable development can be applied in their activities.

An analysis of the management system at the state level, business attitudes, expert opinions and scientific literature made it possible to highlight the sustainable tourism development trends in Russia, which in many ways demonstrate the growing need for the industry transition to the principles of sustainable development.

As a result, the important role of human resources in the industry sustainable development became apparent. The continuous educational activity is the main mechanism for improving competencies, the quality of knowledge and skills of employees. This implies the elaboration of an individual development trajectory for each employee. As a basis for this, we offer an educational model for the tourism industry sustainable development. It is intended for stakeholders in the tourism market and is aimed at raising awareness and building sustainable interaction.

This model can be scalable at different levels and can also be used for foreign countries. In the future, it is necessary to itemize it, as well as the development of a mechanism for the interaction of educational and research organizations, authorities and enterprises of the tourism industry, as well as public and international organizations. Also, the direction of further research is development of a mechanism for interaction among educational and research organizations, authorities, tourism enterprises, and public and international organizations.

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Table. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+		
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+		
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+		
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+		+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+		
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+		
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages		+	
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+		+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+		
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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